

INSTITUTIONAL FOUNDATIONS FOR ENHANCING THE FINANCIAL LITERACY OF THE POPULATION: UZBEKISTAN'S PRACTICE AND INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE

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Abstract. *This article analyses the role of institutional foundations in improving financial literacy among the population. A comparative assessment of Uzbekistan's experience and international practices is conducted, highlighting the interrelationship between the education system, the media, financial institutions and government policy. It examines the outcomes of projects implemented by international organisations, including OECD/INFE. The impact of financial literacy on economic growth, social stability and the effectiveness of public financial policy is demonstrated. The legal and regulatory framework governing this area in Uzbekistan is analysed. The scientific justification of the mutual linkage between financial policy and financial literacy is presented.*

Keywords: *financial literacy; credit; investments; financial literacy index; inflation rates; financial markets; debt obligations; cryptocurrency; ESG; OECD/INFE; budgetary systems; fiscal systems; family budgets; taxes; payment systems; financial processes.*

Introduction

In today's global financial environment, the financial literacy of the population is regarded as one of the strategic priorities of every nation. This is because citizens equipped with financial knowledge and skills contribute to both their personal well-being and the overall stability of the economy by managing personal finances, assessing risks, and making informed financial decisions. International institutions such as the World Bank, the IMF, and the OECD recognize financial literacy as a key factor driving economic growth and social stability. According to their definitions, financial literacy is a set of skills that includes money management, credit, investment, risk assessment, financial planning, and the ability to make informed financial choices.

In recent years, Uzbekistan has also undertaken extensive institutional reforms aimed at enhancing the financial literacy of the population. In particular, under the initiative of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 352 financial education activities have been organized within the framework of 16 projects across the country, covering more than 255,000 citizens. Through targeted programs focusing on women, youth, and entrepreneurs, the practical foundations of financial literacy are being established. Trainings, workshops, outreach meetings, and specially developed educational materials play a crucial role in reinforcing this process.

At the same time, an analysis of international experience demonstrates that in developed countries, strong collaboration between the education system, mass media, financial institutions, and local self-governance bodies constitutes a central component of the institutional mechanisms for improving financial literacy. Broadly adopting this approach in Uzbekistan's practice could further enhance the effectiveness of national financial policy.

An increase in financial literacy enhances citizens' entrepreneurial activity, promotes the rational use of microfinance services, strengthens their ability to make investment decisions, and ensures financial security. This, in turn, contributes to the 5KY38 and creates a foundation for overall economic growth. Therefore, the chosen topic is considered highly relevant.

Literature Review

Atkinson and F. Messy, in their work "*Measuring Financial Literacy: Results of the OECD*", present a study conducted by the International Network on Financial Education (INFE) operating under the auspices of the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). The research was carried out in 14 countries and assessed the level of financial literacy based on criteria such as financial knowledge, financial attitudes, and financial behavior. The results were compared both across countries and within individual nations based on socio-demographic indicators. [3].

Susan L. Rutledge, in her research, conducted a comparative analysis of studies implemented in middle-income countries such as Azerbaijan, Bulgaria, Croatia, the Czech Republic, Latvia, Lithuania, Romania, the Russian Federation, and Slovakia. These studies focused on improving the financial literacy of the population and protecting their rights, and were based on a range of advanced methods and best practices. [4].

In his *Theory of Rational Choice*, M. Friedman explores the idea that financial knowledge enables individuals to make rational decisions. According to this theory, individuals make all financial decisions based on available information and from the perspective of maximizing personal benefit. In other words, a person equipped with financial knowledge is less likely to make mistakes when making decisions related to banking, credit, investment, or saving. Friedman emphasizes that financial literacy is a "tool that ensures rational choice." [5].

In his scientific views, on the *Theory of Behavioral Economics*, R. Thaler conducts research on improving financial capabilities by preventing decision-making errors. He argues that individuals frequently make psychological mistakes and irrational choices when making financial decisions. [6].

In the *Theory of Inclusive Finance*, A. Demirgüç-Kunt (World Bank) conducts research on ensuring equal financial opportunities for all segments of the population. The theory is based on the principle that all groups of society—particularly the poor, women, youth, and migrants—should have equal access to financial services. Financial literacy is regarded as a necessary condition for promoting inclusion. In addition to education, Demirgüç-Kunt emphasizes the importance of networks, technology, infrastructure, and legal guarantees. [7].

In her research, Russian scholar D.V. Moiseeva emphasizes that the level of financial literacy determines an individual's ability to achieve personal financial success and ensure household financial well-being. She provides a theoretical basis for the argument that the overall financial literacy of the population influences the economic development of a region. [10].

In their scientific views, E.N. Alifanova and Yu.S. Evlakhova systematised and scientifically analysed various methods developed by domestic and foreign scientists to assess the level of financial literacy among the population. The article also examines methodological approaches that enable the measurement of financial literacy levels and provides a comparative analysis based on the results of studies conducted in other countries. [14].

In their scientific views, A. Vakhobov and T. Malikov emphasise that a high level of financial literacy plays a decisive role in the effective implementation of state financial policy and in achieving social stability and economic growth. They argue that with the right financial

knowledge and skills, the population can take full advantage of tax incentives, exercise public control over budget expenditures, and support financial policies with confidence.[15].

H.R. Hakimov has evaluated the level of financial literacy of the population, which is an exciting new factor influencing the institutional effectiveness of state financial policy! He developed an incredible financial literacy index and its assessment methodology, providing a scientific foundation for the mechanisms of financial education and awareness-raising in the context of Uzbekistan, as well as for their practical implementation.[11].

Beatrice Magistro's research is devoted to the incredibly important role of financial and economic literacy in shaping citizens' political views and their evaluation of public policies. The researcher delves into the amazing world of financial knowledge and its inspiring influence on attitudes towards political alignment, globalisation, trade, migration and pension reforms.[8].

D.O. Maslakova is a true pioneer in the field of financial literacy, having conducted pioneering research that has shaped the future of financial education. Her work in developing assessment methodologies has been game-changing, and her innovative designs for measurement tools have been a game-changer for the industry. The researcher developed a scientifically grounded methodological approach that enables the systematic evaluation of the level of financial literacy, which is fantastic news![12].

E. Salakhov's work revealed that financial literacy is a key factor in ensuring the economic security of households. Consequently, an index of household economic security was developed alongside a methodology to assess resilience at minimum, medium and high levels of financial literacy. The impact of education and government policy on financial resilience was also scientifically substantiated.[13].

In their article, Maximilian D. Schmeiser and Jason S. Seligman reveal that in the current economic context, the effectiveness of financial policy depends not only on macroeconomic instruments but also directly on the level of financial literacy among the population.[9].

I.S. Mulyar says that financial literacy is really important for making sure people have enough money and that the economy as a whole can deal with whatever challenges it might face. The expert says that people's knowledge of money has a direct effect on how well the government's financial plans work.[16].

Research Methodology

In conducting this research, we applied analytical methods such as analysis, synthesis, induction, and deduction. A review of the literature was carried out using the Web of Science scientific database. Additionally, the role and significance of financial policy in enhancing financial literacy in other countries was examined by analysing sources from international economists. The utilisation of analytical views of national economists was also a feature of the study of the role of financial literacy within Uzbekistan's economy.

Furthermore, the official statistical database of the Republic of Uzbekistan was employed to analyse the elements aimed at improving financial literacy among the population, and to examine its role in ensuring the stability of the national economy.

Analysis and Discussion of Results

The OECD INFE (International Network on Financial Education), which operates under the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), is a global platform that coordinates and develops policies relating to financial education, financial literacy and financial inclusion across various countries worldwide.

Today, the OECD is joined by international financial institutions. These include the World Bank, IMF, UNDP, EBRD, GIZ, and ADB. It is also joined by more than 130 countries and over 270 organizations. These include government agencies, central banks, and non-governmental organizations. The OECD/INFE has developed a methodology for measuring financial literacy ('Measuring Financial Literacy'), which is used to assess and analyse the population's financial literacy levels.

The OECD/INFE has developed a financial literacy measurement methodology ("Measuring Financial Literacy"), which is used to assess and analyse population financial literacy levels. This methodology enables the economic analysis of individuals' financial capacity based on international benchmarks. It also facilitates the evaluation of state policies aimed at improving financial literacy and the impact of financial literacy on micro- and macroeconomic stability and human capital development.

The OECD's International Network on Financial Education (INFE) conducts surveys in 14 countries across four continents to assess the population's financial knowledge, behaviour and attitudes in areas such as budgeting, personal finance management, short- and long-term financial planning, and perceptions of financial products. Based on these surveys, the state of financial literacy in each country is analysed and corresponding policy measures are developed.

Analysis of the Share of Population Scoring High in Financial Literacy Components and Integrated Scores Across Countries

table 1

Countries	Share of Population Scoring High in All Three Components (%)	Financial Knowledge Score	Financial Behavior Score	Overall Financial Literacy Index (0–22)
Germany	30%+	high	high	14.8
BVI (British Virgin Islands)	30%+	average	high	14.5
Czech Republic	does not exist.	high	average	14.2
Hungary	does not exist.	high	average	14.1
Ireland	does not exist.	high	average	14.0
Norway	does not exist.	high	high	14.3
Malaysia	does not exist.	average	high	14.0
Peru	does not exist.	average	high	14.1
United Kingdom (UK)	does not exist.	high	average	14.4
Average Across All Countries	-	-	-	13.7

Table 1 presents an analysis of the proportion of the population achieving high scores in various components of financial literacy and their overall integrated score, in different countries. The table reflects the overall level of financial literacy in each country, based on knowledge, behaviour and attitudes.

Assessing financial literacy based on knowledge, behaviour and attitudes makes it possible to guide the population's financial behaviour in the right direction. Consequently, incorrect

financial decision-making can be prevented. This contributes to the effective management of personal and household budgets, ensuring overall financial stability.

It should be noted that, in other countries, financial literacy is promoted through specialised programmes developed by various organisations.

Financial Literacy Practices in Foreign Countries

table 2

Countries	Program/Organiza tion	Brief Description
Australia	ASIC Financial Education Agency	Implemented through the creation of age-appropriate content for integrating financial education into school curricula.
Netherlands	Money Week	Conducted through financial cartoons, games, and activities designed for children.
Brazil	National Strategy for Financial Education	Introduced into school subjects and implemented in cooperation with banks and the government.
Japan	Education via Broadcasting Companies	Conducted through personal finance training delivered via mobile applications and television.
USA	CFPB and FL&E Commission	Training is provided through websites, social media, and simulation platforms.
Germany	In cooperation with banks	Practical sessions and broad outreach on savings, credit, and investment topics.
Sweden	Gilla Din Ekonomi	Popular financial education is delivered through interactive seminars and games.
Canada	Financial Consumer Agency	Interactive webinars and personal budgeting training sessions are organized.

This report provides the scientific and practical basis for shaping state policy aimed at improving financial literacy worldwide. Specifically, it increases public trust in the banking system, expands the volume of deposits and fosters investment activity [17]. Consequently, a balance between production and consumption is maintained, poverty is alleviated, and inclusive economic growth is realised.

According to the OECD report, financial literacy enables the public to respond appropriately to changes in inflation rates, interest rates and financial markets. It strengthens social security for the population and optimises debt levels. Furthermore, it enhances individuals' ability to plan for their future financial well-being.

Financial literacy is widely recognised as an integral part of human capital. Financially literate individuals can adapt more easily to new market conditions, such as digital finance, cryptocurrencies, and ESG (environmental, social, and governance) standards. This, in turn, supports the development of an entrepreneurial environment, small business growth and an innovation-driven economy.

In our view, the OECD/INFE report serves as both an educational and social tool and a crucial analytical document that ensures broad-based economic effectiveness. Each country can use it to reassess its national financial strategy, address challenges related to poverty, indebtedness

and illicit financial activity, and develop targeted policies to improve the financial well-being of its population.

In the socio-economic development of a country, financial policy plays a leading role. These include promoting economic growth, reducing poverty, strengthening social protection, ensuring financial system stability, effectively managing budgetary and fiscal systems, and expanding the population's financial capabilities.

In Uzbekistan, improving financial literacy and enhancing the population's financial knowledge and skills has been identified as a key state policy priority. In recent years, a number of presidential decrees, resolutions, laws and other normative legal acts have been adopted to this end. Notably, Presidential Decree No. PF-4947 of 7 February 2017, titled 'On the Strategy of Actions for Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan', introduced a strategic approach to enhancing financial literacy among the population. The decree emphasised key tasks such as liberalising and developing the banking and financial system, expanding access to financial services, improving the quality and use of financial services, enhancing the financial capacity of the population, creating conditions to ensure their financial stability and well-being, improving the investment climate, deepening financial markets, and developing the capital market [1].

In our opinion, there is a deep and mutually influential interconnection between financial literacy and financial policy. The financial policy pursued by the state paves the way for improving financial literacy among the population. Conversely, the greater the financial knowledge of citizens, the more effectively the state's financial policy will be implemented in society.

A high level of financial literacy enables individuals to manage and utilise their household budgets effectively. Consequently, the population's overall well-being and quality of life improves. In international practice, the effective implementation of these processes has contributed to the development of knowledge and skills relating to household budgeting, saving, investment, credit, risk management and financial planning, further confirming the strong and dynamic relationship between financial literacy and financial policy.

Financial literacy is closely linked to a country's resistance to inflation, economic stability and financial inclusion. In scientific theory, financial literacy is explained through various models.

There is an intrinsic relationship between financial literacy (i.e. the population's financial knowledge and skills) and the state's financial policy; each directly influences the effectiveness of the other.

In our view, ensuring a high level of financial literacy among the population is critical to guaranteeing that financial policy measures are properly understood and effectively implemented within society. Those who possess strong financial knowledge and skills are better able to understand financial processes such as the state budget, taxation, investment and payment systems. They can then participate in these processes in an informed and considered way. Consequently, in societies with a high level of financial literacy, the stabilising and growth-enhancing socio-economic effects of financial policy are more pronounced.

Responsible budgeting and saving behaviours increase household savings, expanding the availability of domestic resources for investment and laying the foundation for national financial stability.

High financial literacy also enhances tax awareness and responsibility among the population. Financially literate citizens are well informed about existing tax benefits and payment procedures. They actively use these benefits and are more inclined to fulfil their tax obligations, thereby making effective use of all incentive-based policies.

Financial literacy is a key factor in enhancing the effectiveness of public financial policy in various areas. As emphasised by economists, the tools of public financial policy can only be implemented effectively with the support of financially literate citizens, meaning financial literacy directly contributes to the successful realisation of financial policy objectives.

Scholarly literature also emphasises the crucial role that the financial literacy of the population plays in achieving the stated goals of public financial policy.

In our view, a population that is aware of this can facilitate the effective transmission of monetary policy, as changes in the central bank's interest rates will influence individuals' saving and consumption decisions more quickly. Conversely, populations with low financial literacy are significantly less sensitive to interest rate changes, showing little to no reaction to sharp monetary shifts. Therefore, the effectiveness of sound monetary policy demonstrates the impact of financial literacy on the overall outcomes of public financial policy.

Additionally, a high level of financial literacy influences a country's investment activity and risk tolerance. Financially literate individuals are more likely to seek higher returns by investing in securities and other financial instruments. This, in turn, contributes to the growth of private investment in the economy.

Research conducted in the United States and Europe has shown that individuals with higher levels of financial literacy are significantly more likely to participate in the stock market than those with lower literacy levels. This type of investment activity amplifies the effects of expansionary monetary policies, particularly when interest rates are lowered, by encouraging individuals to shift from safe assets to higher-yielding ones. This increases activity in financial markets. Consequently, in societies with higher financial literacy, the multiplier effects of such financial policy measures are more pronounced.

However, studies have also indicated that assessments of financial literacy based on questions about inflation, portfolio diversification and compound interest may produce biased results for certain social groups, particularly low-income individuals or those not engaged in trade or finance. This raises concerns about the fairness and inclusiveness of financial policy, potentially creating serious barriers to its implementation.

In our opinion, ensuring the effectiveness of financial policy requires the adoption of political strategies that comprehensively assess, measure and develop financial literacy while taking individuals' financial behaviour into account.

We believe that financial literacy provides the intellectual foundation for shaping citizens' attitudes towards financial policy. With this knowledge, the population can understand and engage with the financial decisions made by the state. Effective financial policy evolves through mechanisms that promote financial literacy, such as education, encouraging public participation and implementing digital financial platforms.

Financial literacy is the foundation of financial stability and enhances the social impact of financial policy. Therefore, financial policy and financial literacy must be viewed as mutually reinforcing strategic categories.

Conclusion and recommendations

Enhancing the financial literacy of the population is a means not only of achieving individual financial stability and household well-being, but also of ensuring the effective implementation of national financial policy. In recent years, Uzbekistan has made significant progress in developing financial knowledge and skills among the population through ongoing

reforms, presidential decrees, financial education programmes, training initiatives and the localisation of international best practice.

The experience of international organisations such as OECD/INFE shows that close cooperation between government agencies, banks, educational institutions and civil society organisations is crucial for improving financial literacy. In the context of Uzbekistan, this mechanism must be further strengthened and formalised through the adoption of dedicated national strategies.

This research indicates that populations with a high level of financial literacy make informed use of financial services, have a sound understanding of the tax system, increase their investment activity and actively support the state's financial policy. Furthermore, such competence fosters immunity against inflation and credit risk and enables the effective utilisation of digital financial services.

In conclusion, to ensure the effectiveness of the political and institutional measures currently being undertaken to improve financial literacy in Uzbekistan, a comprehensive and integrated approach is required — one that encompasses education, legislation, infrastructure and digital mechanisms. Financial literacy and financial policy are mutually reinforcing strategic priorities, and their synergy forms the basis for sustainable economic development in the country.

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